

Research

Deep Neural Network Based Self-Tuning PID Control for Quadrotor Attitude

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Abstract: For decades, the Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) controllers have been successfully used in academia and industry for several types of plants. This is due to its versatility and sufficient efficiency in linear or linear plants and in such circumstances in non-linear plants. A variety of PID controller gains tuning methods have been suggested in the Quadrotor Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) literature over the last decades, several of them off-line. However, in those situations the plant is exposed to persistent parametric shifts or external disturbances, online gain tuning is a suitable alternative. This is the case for the UAV quadrotor, where the parameters linked to weight are being applied to the mass adjustment according to the system to which it is attached. In practice, some time is spent on tuning the PID gains in the UAV attitude. Once the best range of gains has been made, the UAV is able to start off smoothly. However, as the UAV changes are subject to winds, their output deteriorates as the fixed set of gains is no longer true under the current conditions. In order to solve this problem, an online PID gains tuning algorithm should be introduced. This paper proposes an auto-tune PID controller based on Deep Neural Networks (DNN). The DNN plays the function of automatically calculating the required range of PID gains to achieve device stability. The DNN changes the online benefits of the controller to obtain a smaller location monitoring malfunction. Simulation results are provided taking into account the under-implemented 6 DOF (degrees of freedom) Quadrotor UAV. Real-time tests on Quadrotor test-bench are conducted to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed scheme.

Keywords: Auto-Tuning, Deep Neural Networks, PID, Quadrotor Attitude Control

1. Introduction

In the past few decades, the robotics community and leading institutions have shown an increasing interest in autonomous UAVs with a great deal of handy techniques implemented on UAVs flying platforms are also becoming broadly available. Quadrotor UAV's are the most popular of these architectures having a significant shift in the past years because they are

mechanically simple, they do not require complex mechanical parts to control flight, they can move and fly only by changing motor speed, they can promptly perceive the environment in any orientation and analyze information autonomously. Very often, according to the task, the quadrotor is required to continuously change its mechanical setups or windows disturbance or carry loads causing a change in behavior. That results as an inherent change in its weight, sensitivity to disturbance, strong decoupling, and nonlinearity and as a consequence, a decrease in the attitude performance. In addition, quadrotor have to deal with the highly dynamical disturbance environment represented in the form of winds and obstacles. With this in mind, when the dynamic characteristics of the system are time dependent or the operating conditions of the system vary, it is necessary to re-tune the gains to obtain the desired performance, resulting in time consumption. In this paper, a Deep Neural Networks (DNN) self-tuning algorithm is proposed to automatically tune the gains of the PID controller. The optimum set of gains is calculated digitally with less computing work by using the expected and real state variables. The self-tuning process prevents time-consuming manual tuning of the PID controller and guarantees improved performance by supplying PID controller settings as the device dynamics or operating points shift.

Intelligent control methods involve a fuzzy neural network controller optimized for the quadrotor in terms of control and monitoring precision. [1–4], They have been commonly used to monitor and have become an accurate alternative, although these algorithms take a long time of preparation and tuning. Control schemes vary from tracking to dynamic positioning [4,5] where their primary goal is to measure and prepare for the unpredictable forces of shifting conditions. Study: Research [7–14] present systems with a combination of neural networks and fuzzy control, in which training and behavioral laws are based on the desired states. Their output is defined as accurate when the instability and disruptions arise when the trajectory is underway. While training cycles are incredibly long, there are also combinations of PID controls and a smart device programmed to auto-tune the benefits of various systems, such as: sub-aquatic [15,16], nonlinear [18–21], and others: [23–25]. This paper implements an online Deep Neural Networks (DNN) auto-tune PID controller on Quadrotor unmanned aerial vehicle (UAVs); for attitude and trajectory monitoring with unknown disturbances.

Simulation results are provided taking into account the non-linear dynamics of the UAV, including disturbances. Real-time quadrotor tests are performed to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed scheme. For the remaining sections of this paper, see Section 2, the General Quadrotor System Model of UAV, Section 3 Auto-Tuning Neural Network for PID Control,

Section 4 describes the simulation results, and Finally in Section 5 the concluding remarks are provided.

2. General Quadrotor System Model

This section presents the quadrotor's nonlinear dynamic model, which provides the basis for the Section 3 controller replication. The frame of the coordinates and the system setup are shown in Figure 1 with X_b axis pointing forward, Y_b axis pointing right, and Z_b axis pointing up. The quadrotor has an x-configuration with four motors and the direction of rotation is as specified in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The free-body diagram of the quadrotor x-configuration

The inputs command to the nonlinear model δ_n are the standardized pulse-width-modulation (PWM) signals via the motors electronic-speed-controller (ESCs) and the model outputs are 3-dimensional position vector $P_w = (x, y, z)^T$ in world frame and the Euler angles vector $\Phi = (\phi, \theta, \psi)^T$ in the aerospace sequence of $(\psi \rightarrow \theta \rightarrow \phi)^T$.

The quadrotor has six degrees of freedom, including three position variables and three attitude angle variables. Because of its special characteristics, under-actuated, strong coupling and sensitive to disturbance, it is very difficult to establish its dynamical model accurately. In order to establish the model of the quadrotor, the fixed frame E and body frame B must be established firstly [34,35], the lift force analysis diagram is shown in Figure 1. The position coordinates can determine the relative location between the quadrotor body frame B and the fixed frame E, attitude angles can determine the flight attitude of the quadrotor. Let RE B (θ, ϕ, ψ) denote the transformation matrix between fixed frame E and body frame B that using Euler–Lagrange formulation, which can be expressed as:

$$R_{EB}(\theta, \phi, \psi) = [R_1 R_2 R_3] \quad (1)$$

Where

$$R_1 \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \cos \theta \\ \sin \psi \cos \theta \\ -\sin \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_2 \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \sin \phi \sin \theta - \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \sin \psi \sin \phi \sin \theta + \cos \psi \cos \phi \\ \cos \theta \sin \phi \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_3 \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi + \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \sin \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi + \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \cos \theta \cos \phi \end{bmatrix}$$

according to the lift force analysis from Figure. 1, the lift forces of the quadrotor in the body frame {B} can be expressed as:

$$F_B = \begin{bmatrix} F_{XB} \\ F_{YB} \\ F_{ZB} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

from equations (1) and (2), the lift forces of the quadrotor in the fixed frame {E} can be calculated by

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_X \\ F_Y \\ F_Z \end{bmatrix} = R_{EB} \cdot F_B = \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 F_i \right) \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi \sin \theta \cos \phi + \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \sin \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi - \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \cos \theta \cos \phi \end{bmatrix}$$

then, the translational movement of the quadrotor can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = (F_x - k_f x) / m \\ \dot{y} = (F_y - k_f y) / m \\ \dot{z} = (F_z - mg - k_f z) / m \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and also, the rotational movement of the quadrotor can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\theta} = l(-F_1 + F_2 + F_3 - F_4 - k_f \theta) / l_2 + (l_3 + l_1) \phi \psi / l_2 \\ \dot{\phi} = l(-F_1 + F_2 + F_3 - F_4 - k_f \phi) / l_1 + (l_2 + l_3) \phi \psi / l_1 \\ \dot{\psi} = [k_c(-F_1 + F_2 + F_3 - F_4) - k_f \psi] / l_3 + (l_1 + l_2) \theta \phi / l_3 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Combining the equations (3) and (4), the mathematical model [36–37] of the quadrotor UAV flight system can be represented as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = (F_x - k_f x) / m \\ \dot{y} = (F_y - k_f y) / m \\ \dot{z} = (F_z - mg - k_f z) / m \\ \dot{\theta} = l(-F_1 + F_2 + F_3 - F_4 - k_f \theta) / l_2 + (l_3 + l_1) \phi \psi / l_2 \\ \dot{\phi} = l(-F_1 + F_2 + F_3 - F_4 - k_f \phi) / l_1 + (l_2 + l_3) \phi \psi / l_1 \\ \dot{\psi} = [k_c(-F_1 + F_2 + F_3 - F_4) - k_f \psi] / l_3 + (l_1 + l_2) \theta \phi / l_3 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where x , y , z are the positions of the quadrotor, θ is the pitch angle, ϕ is the roll angle and ψ is the yaw angle, F_1 , F_3 , F_2 , F_4 are the lift forces of the four rotors respectively, and other system parameters are shown in Table 1. In order to simplify the design procedures and the presentation of the quadrotor flight system, the virtual control variables of the whole system U_1 , U_2 , U_3 , U_4 are introduced to transform with the lift forces F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , F_4 , the variable transformation formula can be expressed as formula (6), and U_x , U_y , U_z as the virtual control inputs in the position loop, which is given by the formula (7)

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ u_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{m} & \frac{1}{m} & \frac{1}{m} & \frac{1}{m} \\ \frac{-1}{l_2} & \frac{1}{l_2} & \frac{1}{l_2} & \frac{1}{l_2} \\ \frac{-1}{l_1} & \frac{1}{l_1} & \frac{1}{l_1} & \frac{1}{l_1} \\ \frac{-k_c}{l_3} & \frac{k_c}{l_3} & \frac{k_c}{l_3} & \frac{k_c}{l_3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_1 \\ F_2 \\ F_3 \\ F_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

From (5), (6) and (7), the mathematical model of the quadrotor flight system can be rewritten as

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ u_z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{(F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4)}{m} \times \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi + \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \sin \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi - \sin \phi \cos \psi \\ \cos \theta \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = u_x - k_f x / m \\ \dot{y} = u_y - k_f y / m \\ \dot{z} = u_z - mg - k_f z / m \\ \dot{\theta} = u_2 - k_f \theta / l_2 + (l_3 + l_1) \phi \psi / l_2 \\ \dot{\phi} = u_3 - k_f \phi / l_1 + (l_2 + l_3) \theta \psi / l_1 \\ \dot{\psi} = u_4 - k_f \psi / l_3 + (l_1 + l_2) \theta \phi / l_3 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and now combining the equations (6) and (7), the real control inputs in the position loop can be calculated by

$$u_1 = \frac{u_z}{\cos \phi \cos \theta} \quad (9)$$

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{u_x \cos \psi + u_y \sin \psi}{u_z}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$\phi = \arctan\left(\cos \theta \frac{u_x \sin \psi + u_y \cos \psi}{u_z}\right) \quad (11)$$

the expressions of θ and ϕ will be used in the following design process as intermediate variables.

3. Auto Tuning Deep Neural Network For PID Control

The tuning of the PID controllers depends on changing its parameters (K_p ; K_i ; K_d) to ensure that the performance of the device under control is stable and reliable in compliance with the specified performance criteria. The proposed auto-tuning algorithm is based on the DNN which has the following characteristics:

- 1) Parallelism and generalization. A DNN are able to produce useful outputs for inputs not provided under the learning phase.
- 2) Non-linearity. A DNN can be linear or not allowing it to represent systems generated by nonlinear guidelines.
- 3) Adaptability. DNN are capable of re-adjusting weights and adapting to new environmental situations. This is especially useful when the system offers non-stationary data, that is, the properties involved by the system vary over time.

- 4) Fault tolerance. When an operational failure occurs on a local part of the network, it lightly affects the global performance.

This property is attributed to the distributive existence of the stored data processed along the neural network. Fully in line with above, this work is based on a back-propagation deep neural network, which also meets the desired characteristics to accomplish the goal tasks. Recurrent networks with supervised learning structured with delay are widely used in miniature vehicles as mentioned in [17,18], as well as for linear systems with large uncertainties in their surrounding environment as shown in [5,29–31].

3.1. Control Law

Based on the system dynamic mode developed in the last section, the nested controller system is eventually designed to control the quadrotor attitude and horizontal speed. As showed in figure 2, the attitude controller, is developed. It receives user commands, and desired attitude commands and controls the quadrotor accordingly by taking the feedback measurement from inertial measurement unit (IMU), altitude and velocity sensor onboard. In the discrete time domain, the digital PID algorithm can be expressed as follows [17]:

$$t(n) = t(n-1) + K_p(e(n) - e(n-1)) + K_i e(n) + K_d(e(n) - 2e(n-1) + e(n-2)) \quad (12)$$

where $\tau(n)$ is the original control signal, $e(n) = \eta_d - \eta$ represents the position tracking error, η_d denotes the desired trajectory, K_p is the proportional gain, K_i the integral gain, K_d the derivative gain, and n the sample time. A block diagram of the auto-tuning control with artificial neural network (ANN) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Block diagram of an auto-tuned PID with artificial NN control.

3.2. Attitude Controller

The attitude controller nested inside the altitude and velocity controllers, it receives desired roll ϕ^* desired pitch θ^* , and total thrust command T_{total}^* total, from them, as well as the desired yaw command ψ^* from the user. Then with the help of attitude feedback measurement, Φ from IMU, it commands normalized PWM signals, u_n^* to the four ESCs. It is designed to minimize the attitude error, while maintaining the total thrust, T_{total} as commanded. The attitude errors e_θ , is defined as:

$$e_\theta = \Phi^* - \Phi = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \phi \\ \Delta \theta \\ \Delta \psi \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Where desired attitude is $\Phi^* = (\phi^*, \theta^*, \psi^*)$ and angle deviations

are $\Delta \phi = \phi^* - \phi$, $\Delta \theta = \theta^* - \theta$, $\Delta \psi = \psi^* - \psi$. This expression of error guarantees stability only when angle deviations are small. A more sophisticated error expression will be implemented in future work (ADRC). Then, we can apply the proportional, integral and derivative error to obtain the PID control law, and attitude correction vector, u_ϕ can be computed by:

$$u_\phi(n) = u_\phi(n-1) + K_p(e(n) - e(n-1)) + K_i e(n) + K_d(e(n) - 2e(n-1) + e(n-2)) \quad (14)$$

where gain K_p , K_i , K_d can be the self-tuned parameters, depending on the aggressiveness of the required manoeuvre. This correction vector must be linear to the moment, that we should apply to quadrotor to compensate the attitude error. Finally, to generate the normalized PWM signal command, for individual rotor, Therefore, the thrust command T for individual rotors can be computed by:

$$T^* = \begin{bmatrix} 1_{4 \times 1} & C^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_{total}^* / 4 \\ u_\phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Where $T^* = (T_1^*, T_2^*, T_3^*, T_4^*)$ then we can compute the output commands u_n by:

$$u_n^* = \sqrt{\frac{T_n^*}{cT} + c_o} \quad (16)$$

3.3. Algorithm Auto Tuning

The algorithm used as auto-tuning is the back-propagation (backprop, BP) method, chosen for its ability to adapt to changing environments. Operation begins applying the inputs to the network as illustrated in Figure 3, this is propagated from the first layer to the hidden layers in, up to produce an output (K_p , K_i , K_d). The output signal is compared to the desired output and an error signal is calculated for each of the outputs, this is shown in Figure 2. The error outputs BP, starting from the output layer, to all neurons in the hidden layer that contribute directly to the output; however, the hidden layer neurons receive only a fraction of the total error signal. This process repeats iteratively, layer by layer, until all neurons in the network has received an error signal describing its relative contribution to the total error.

Figure 3 presents the topology of the DNN used to auto-tune the PID control gains implemented on the quadrotor platform. Its structure shows seven neurons on the input layer, three neurons on the hidden layer, and finally another three neurons on the output layer. The neurons placed on the output layer correspond to the PID gains: K_p , K_i , K_d .

Figure 3. Block diagram of the implemented backprop DN

where $u(n)$ and $u(n - 1)$ are reference inputs (desired trajectory), $y(n)$ and $y(n - 1)$ are reference outputs (real trajectory), $C(n)$ and $C(n - 1)$ correspond to the control signals, w_{ji} are the weights of the hidden layer, and v_{ji} are the weights of the output layer. The back-propagation algorithm looks for the minimum of the error function in weight space using the method of gradient descent [3]. The combination of weights which minimizes the error function is considered to be a solution of the learning problem. The activation functions for back-propagation networks are the sigmoid, a real function $sc : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, 1)$ defined by the expression.

$$h_j = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-s_j}} \quad (17)$$

$$S_j = \sum_{i=1}^3 w_{ji} x_i$$

The output of the j hidden layer neuron may be calculated by means of:

$$E(n) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^t e_y(k)^2 \quad (18)$$

The shape of the sigmoid changes according to the value of h_j . At the same time, the output layer neuron value will be:

$$u(n) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-r}} \quad (19)$$

Where

$$r = \sum_{j=1}^3 v_j h_j \quad (20)$$

The criteria used to minimize the error correspond to Rojas et al. [32], as:

$$E(n) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^t e_y(k)^2 \quad (21)$$

Where $e_y(k) = y_r(n) - y(n)$,

The minimization procedure consists, as it is known, in a movement in the negative gradient direction of the function $E(n)$ with respect to the weighting coefficients v_{ji} and w_{ji} . The $E(n)$ gradient is a multi-dimensional vector [3] whose components are the partial derivative. The weighting coefficients of the input layer are

$$\frac{\partial E(n)}{\partial v_{ji}} = \partial^1 h_j \frac{\partial e_y}{\partial e_u} \quad (22)$$

The weighting coefficient of the hidden layer are

$$\frac{\partial E(n)}{\partial w_{ji}} = -\partial^2 x_i \frac{\partial e_y}{\partial e_u} \quad (23)$$

Using Equations (22) and (23), the adjustments of weighting coefficients v_{ji} Equation (24),

w_{ji} Equation (25) can be made by means of the expressions:

$$v_{ji}(n+1) = v_{ji}(n) + \left(a \frac{\partial e_y}{\partial e_u}\right) \delta^2 h_j \quad (24)$$

$$w_{ji}(n+1) = w_{ji}(n) + \left(a \frac{\partial e_y}{\partial e_u}\right) \delta_j^2 h_j \quad (25)$$

where a is the learning coefficient, $w_{ji}(n+1)$ is a vector of weights for the hidden layer, $v_{ji}(n+1)$ is the vector of weights of the output layer and equivalent gain $\frac{\partial e_y}{\partial e_u}$ is unknown.

4. Simulation Results

Simulation studies of the proposed self-tuned PID was evaluated using MATLAB/Simulink software and python (matplotlib). The effectiveness and advantages of the proposed self-tuned PID scheme are presented by comparative performances with the classical PID control. Set the initial position coordinates of the quadrotor as $[0, 0, 0]$ while the initial attitude is $[0, 0, 0]$. Denoted $\omega_1(t)$, $\omega_2(t)$ and $\omega_3(t)$ as the system external disturbances added to the three attitude channels respectively, which are given by

$$\begin{cases} \omega_1(t) = \text{sign}(\sin(0.9t)) \\ \omega_2(t) = \text{sign}(\sin(0.9t)) + \cos(0.3t) \\ \omega_3(t) = 0.5 \text{sign}(\sin(0.5t)) + \cos(0.3t) + 2 \cos(0.9t) \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

4.1. Attitude Gains Simulation

Simulation 1: Figures 4–6 indicate the gains (K_p , K_i , K_d) obtained by the neural network in every $\Phi^* = (\phi^*, \theta^*, \phi^*)$ as can be seen, neurons start working from time zero since they absorbed the first disturbance of 20s in length, and respond to the abrupt change presented

when the second perturbation is introduced, thus allowing change of the neural network in order to compensate for the lack of gains in corresponding to the alterations.

Figure 4. PID gain time behavior in the pitch angle

Figure 5. PID gain time behavior in roll angle.

Figure 6. PID gain time behavior in yaw angle.

Simulation 2: The auto-tuned PID was evaluated using simulation results shown in Figure 7, bellow presents the model-based quadrotor dynamic and control behaviour of the quadrotor x-configuration. The simulation is done with *Numpy* and *Matplotlib* python packages. The

dynamic inputs is a simple non-linear second order and the parameters are set to roughly match the characteristics of the designed quadrotor dynamic, and the rotor thrust and torque coefficients have been measured.

Figure 7. Attitude response

Trajectory generation and path tracking, for both position and heading. In the simulation script, the desired position and heading way-points can be set along with the time for each waypoint.

Figure 8. Real trajectory (*green*) vs. desired trajectory (*blue*), with disturbance.

Finally, In order to decide when the Deep neural PID is doing best, the test was split into three phases corresponding to: when no disturbance happened, and where the disturbance was applied, as can be seen in Figure 9. Once again, to equate the auto-tuned PID vs. the

conventional PID controller with the set gains, the MSE of each step has been obtained and is used, in figure 9.

Figure 9. Conventional PID Controller vs auto-tune PID, segmented in 3 phases of 1 m each

5. Conclusions

The actual work presents the development of a control algorithm to automatically tune the gains of a PID control, based on a neural network. The control algorithm was implemented on quadrotor dynamic model for attitude and trajectory tracking with unknown disturbances. The algorithm performance was evaluated in two instances: gains simulation and quadrotor attitude response performance in real-time. The numerical simulation took place with the non-linear second order model equations; including disturbances of winds in different directions. A comparative study between the conventional PID and the auto-tuned PID proposed was discussed. It can be seen from the results that the total disturbance error of the system was compensated by DNN thus obtaining a better attitude, and anti-disturbance performance, even with significant disturbance.

For the application of the DNN auto-tuning in the attitude control of quad-rotor UAV, we will use the actual quad-rotor UAV to verify the actual effect, and complete the transition from theory to practice in the future work.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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